

HOW TO DO GENDER WITH SHOPPING SPACE DESIGN?

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ABSTRACT

This article has a triple assignment. First, I will briefly review the body of knowledge on gender performance and practice theory, which pertains to design of shopping space, to present dual nature of shopping and its space, in which it is the basic hypothesis of this article. Second, equally importantly, I will locate effective empirical research established on the S-O-R pattern with main findings in fields of consumer's psychology and behavior related with environment design. Last, and of the most challenge, my specific intent is to clarify the network weaved by three dimensions, involving women's gender identity as pleasure hunter, space design as acting stage and consumption as social practice. Space designers, with gender awareness highlighted here, would be more sensible and caring in future projects. Design, in this case, can be approaching its maximum value for the our society - humanity and harmony.

Keywords: shopping space, environmental stimuli, gender, practice

INTRODUCTION

Shopping, the most significant practice in contemporary everyday life, is transforming us both physically and emotionally, as Falk and Campbell (1997) put it. A double lens on shopping space is proposing here: one which, on one hand, presenting shopping site in its cultural and theoretical contemplation through the view of gender identities of it's main consumers - urban women, and, on the other, restoring shopping space into its marketing and business context by the way of empirical research with psychological and behavioral concern. Issues of shopping space have not been caught by researcher of marketing, geography, psychology and urban plan until the 1980s; in the next decade, social

scientists have embarked upon taking shopping and its experience as core topics (Ng, 2003).

THEORETICAL FOCUSES: SHOPPING MATTERS AND GENDER PERFORMED

SHOPPING DOES MATTER

Shopping has grown to be a significant theme in marketing (Tauber, 1972), psychology (Mehrabian and Russell, 1974), anthropology (Appadurai, 1986), gender theory (Moore, 1991), cultural studies (Miller, 1998), and fashion studies (Buckley & Fawcett, 2002), on account of it's, as Falk et al., (1997: 10) indicated "a paradigmatic case illustrating the fundamental shift in the structuring principle of society from production to consumption." Coherence between environmental design and consumer's behavior, however, was seldom elucidated with the angle of gender.

Sprouted from the ideal of public space and social communities for women to experience modernity, shopping in its nature, networked with subjectivity, status, sense of being, lifestyle and fashion, has been bonded intimately to women's gender identities (Adburgham, 1979; McKendrick et al., 1982; Miller, 1998; Dittmar & Halliwell, 2008; Dunn, 2008).

Alongside of the huge transformation went through by shopping space from the first department store Bon Marché found in 1852 to today's giant mall, changes of women's gender identities have been taking place. It's easy to visualize the varieties of design differences existing between the old-style and contemporary shopping spaces, however, they also share essentials in common. On the one hand, shopping space was turned into adult playground for modern women, like William (1982: 67) revealed, "active verbal interchange between customer and retailer was replaced by the passive, mute response of consumer to things", which allocating more importance to design policy by which profits could be guaranteed. On the other hand, "palace/panorama

/playground/theater”, of which was labeled as the most outstanding badge to the department store in the nineteenth century; they also have been inherited by current shopping space design as the leitmotif. “A dazzling spectacle, splendidly shop fronts and alluring display” (Nava, 1997: 64) which was used to describe the Oxford Street in the late eighteenth century, is precisely appropriate to today’s shopping scenario.

Space design constitutes a background and physical surroundings for practice of shopping, especially for women who spend much more time and interests on consumption (Marchand, 1985; Buttle, 1992; Stewart, 1993; Campbell, 1997), and shopping as bodily involvement performs consciousness of gender identities with visual pleasure incubated from atmospheric effects made by designer.

GENDER PERFORMED BY SHOPPING: THEORY OF PRACTICE AND STRUCTURE-AGENCY

Here are two basic assumptions before moving on: one of which is shopping is explored as practice; the other is that, consumption by women, happening in shopping places, such as department store, shopping center and mall, occurs as a fluid narrative constituting women’s gender identities.

Practice is not an original concept applied in the context of consumption when Warde put it in 2005, however, “consumption as a practice” began to be noticed in theory of practice. In this article, shopping as practice which falls into the idea conceptualized by Reckwitz (2002: 249) who stated, “A ‘practice’ . . . is a routinized type of behaviour which consists of several elements, interconnected to one another: forms of bodily activities, forms of mental activities, ‘things’ and their use, a background knowledge in the form of understanding, know-how, states of emotion and motivational knowledge.” Woman, while she owns right of self-governing to make decision in shopping, becomes an agent, even though she is still regulated and restrained by the structure that existed as enclosure of practice. In such manner, practice theory was combined with structure-agency debate (Barker, 2005) as well as performance argument. As Warde (2005: 134) told, “Practices are thus coordinated entities but also require performance for their existence. A performance presupposes a practice.”

Space shaping people shapes the space, in this paper, emphasis would be laid upon the former part. Design strategies implemented in commercial spaces contribute to the stage/theater/platform for performance of women’s gender identities.

How to do gender with shopping? Gender, is one type of identities attached with consciousness and sense of being subject who as an agent processes autonomy of decision-making. In a male-dominated society and culture, thus, practice of shopping means substantially to women. Making choice about where, when, what and how to purchase everyday necessities for family and to pursue desirable experience for self outlines what a modern, fashionable and independent woman looks like. Freedom of consumption, however, implies multiple possibilities of whom she could be; meanwhile, environment stimuli of shopping space are the other critical contributions to decisions-making process. It explains why shopping space was featured as the “institutional arenas” (West and Zimmerman, 1987:126). As one of the most convincing discourses of lifestyle and mundane practice, shopping displays a far greater impact on the mechanism of formation of self-image and performance of gender identity (Bauman, 1988; Giddens, 1991; Beck, 1992). With feed of functional needs and spiritual desires, shopping “give(s) material form to a particular narrative of self-identity.” (Giddens, 1991:81) Female consumer determines boundaries between “self” and “other” by practice of shopping, to be more exact, by performance of gender identity in shopping space where there are overwhelming selection of goods easily accessible as properties to portray role, spectacular visual arrangement of merchandises, scheme of lighting and color, wall decoration as the arousal atmosphere to be indulged in, combined with adventure-invited and labyrinthine floor layout as stage to exhibit their highly feminine gender identities. Women, in this case, with shopping facilitation, “become the agents of their own livelihood mediated by the market.” (Beck, 1992:130) Performance of gender identity sustained with practice of shopping and discourse of design, was “translated into one of the possession of desired goods and the pursuit of artificially framed style of life.” (Giddens, 1991:198) Assembly of gender identity, to a greater or lesser extent, constitutes

mainstream of consumer's response psychologically and physically. In Bauman (1988:66)'s word, "the act of purchase is presented as the only road to certainty."

"Shopping does matter" becomes the consensus needlessly much more annotation added amongst most of scholars who concerns the consumer culture and identity issues; Like Warde (1994: 882) explained, "It matters because it seriously affects self-identity, being a critical part of the creation and maintenance of a valued sense of self." Elaborate design of shopping environment dilutes scent of its commercial nature, meanwhile condenses its cultural taste, and turns practice of consumption in shopping space into a socially communicated activity.

As mentioned above, shopping has been perceived by its double essence: one as meaning exchange which was the keynote of theoretical studies; the other as material consumption with commerce-oriented emphasis which was discussed in framework of marketing and environmental design by empirical research, which will be approaching in coming part.

EMPIRICAL MODELS: BASED ON THE S-O-R PARADIGM

CROSSOVER TERMINOLOGY REVIEW

It's necessary to accentuate some crossover terms, by virtue of my intent is to juxtapose multiple kinds of studies, which overlaps between domain of environmental psychology and field of space design, "atmospheric effect" is the initiative. As a marketing tool, "atmospherics" was elucidated by Kotler (1973) in the system of manipulated elements to guide and influence behavior of consumer. Kotler's contribution was acknowledged and promoted by followers (Donovan & Rossiter, 1982; Donovan et al., 1994; Gardner et al., 1986; Darden & Babin, 1994; Schlosser, 1998).

Designer, being an operator of shopping space, whose methodologies such as color and lighting, layout and wayfinding, as well as display and decoration, made deliberate efforts to inspire purchase-enhancement response of consumer. Different designs of physical surroundings diversify consumer's feedback to shopping space in details, including lingering time, loyalty, temper, degree of satisfaction and pleasure with consumption

experience (Park et al., 1989; Baker et al., 1994; Spangenberg et al., 1996; Wakefield & Baker, 1998; Kumar & Karande, 2000; Baron et al., 2001; Baker et al., 2002; Arnold et al., 2005).

Glancing over the Kotlerian atmospheric research, it's facile to find out that they generally conformed to the basic pattern of environmental psychology: Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R), which had been widely accepted, introduced by Mehrabian and Russell (1974). S-O-R paradigm advanced a wise theoretical hypothesis which was also feasible to empirical research. It described a systematic simultaneous operational control model, in which, environmental stimuli as input variables were able to launch organism's reaction especially in the sense of emotional and psychological way, and to cause series of behaviors as output. This framework, similarly, had been altered by updated formula of "[Object-Situation]-Person-Behavior" by Belk (1975), and moved further with the model of "Consumption-Emotion-Value" by Holbrook (1986).

ENVIRONMENTAL STIMULI IN SHOPPING SPACE

In this part, I will focus on the stimuli of environment from perspective of space design; then, organism and response would be discussed in the sight of gender identity. Atmospheric elements in shopping space are complicated and assorted, therefore, which have been segmented into four types by Berman and Evans (1995): external varies, general interior variables, layout and design variables, and point-of-purchase and decoration variables. One can conclude effortlessly from the findings of Berman and Evan who proposed the four-type system were deduced from evident standpoint of marketing studies. Environmental stimuli, to a larger degree, are almost chained to the discourse of design. So, shifting to the position of design studies in this paper, environmental stimuli are converged into the following three aspects: lighting & color, layout & wayfinding, and display & decoration.

Color & Lighting

A huge corpus of literature work on the color psychology has been done, of which six kinds of topics were presented for the most part: psychopathology of color, physiological analysis of color, preferences of color, emotional reaction to

color, behavioral dimension of color, and color perception (Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994). Color is the fundamental element in design of shopping space, however, a majority of research related to color was carried out through the eyes of marketing and psychology on point-of-purchase graphic strategies, such as advertisements and packaging, rather than by design studies, which at the same time inferring a larger room for the further exploration on color issues in atmospheric settings (Turley & Milliman, 2000).

From the angle of consumer psychology, color is glued to mood, motive and inclination of shopper. Proper colors were used by retailer to create enriched ambience which spurring wallet drawing-out decision (Bellizzi et al., 1983; Bellizzi & Hite, 1992). Research has found out, in the stylish stores with aims of promoting high classic fashion, blue tone rather than the orange one, was more likely to inspire the positive enthusiastic attitude, coupled with the greater possibility of buying intentions (Babin et al., 2003). Besides effects caused by tone of color on purchase incidence, stronger allurements of visual display (Bellizzi et al., 1983), delightful and excited experience in store (Crowley, 1993), willingness of lingering (Bellizzi & Hite, 1992) and diversified emotional reactions (Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994), have been declared by numerous field experiments.

Since general practice of shopping happens in enclosed and interior space, except for color element, lighting in retailing is another indispensable factor which tightly correlating with profit-earning. Retailer made use of lighting to create a desirable consuming paradise: catch shoppers' eyes, provide them a bright and clear visual requisition to assess and compare commodities, and promote purchase-friendly atmosphere with reasonable cost. Influence of lighting also got attention from extensive empirical research (Baker et al., 1992; Areni & Kim, 1994; Baker, et al., 2002), which have discovered soft, warm and bright illumination situation in shopping space activate the deeper intercourse between consumer and goods. However, in more complicated and greater scale shopping space, like shopping mall or center, impact of lighting was not so firmly connected to the response of shoppers,

such as time of staying and sales ratio (Areni & Kim, 1994; Wakefield & Baker, 1998).

It's noteworthy that neither the probing into color nor the inquiry on lighting was gendered awareness, even though there is an inconvenient truth that women are the mainstream of patronage in shopping space.

Layout & Wayfinding

Gender indifference is pervasive phenomena in empirical research of environmental stimuli. It had not been changed until when it came to the discussion of layout and wayfinding. Taking layout and wayfinding as parallel conception into the same category, for "layout" shows attitude of designer while "wayfinding" displays position of shoppers especially for women consumers who have less knowledge on geographic location.

Classification of layout and wayfinding, not only pertains to issues of space plan for designer and retailer, but also regarding spatial ability of shopper. From the viewpoint of merchandiser, financial benefit is the priority in which keep-wandering walking network may be the best option, rather than the rationality-maximum layout; while for those task-oriented consumers in high time-pressure, efficient and logical route towards the targeted site is their preference.

Wayfinding is an idea which originated by Passini (1977) in his Ph.d thesis, and then expounded by series of further research (1984, 1990, 1996). In Passini's (1984: 46) definition, wayfinding is a versatile capability to location assignment, "wayfinding is the cognitive ability to assimilate spatial information, make maps to find one's way, make decisions and execute these decisions." Case study presided by Dogu and Erkip (2000) discovered how geographic environmental stimuli were specifically empowered by design elements which have bearing on spatial behavioral response of shopper, such as architecture arrangement, visual mapping clarity, route planning guidance, and visible directional sign system.

Realization on gendered difference of geographic knowledge between men and women, to some degree, equals to stereotyped thinking mode which was pervasive in the studies of wayfinding: men were better map-locator than women in shopping space

(Harris, 1981; Linn & Petersen, 1985; Ward et al., 1986; Voyer et al., 1995; Harrell et al., 2000). More accurately, Chebat et al (2003) confirmed the findings created by Goldin and Thorndyke (1982) about two different types of people dealing with wayfinding: visualizers and verbalizers. The former goes to males who are inclined to locate site by visual messages of shopping space, as the latter belongs to females who prefer to track place by verbal information. In other words, men are likely to do shopping by self-service of mapping while women are possibly to go shopping in group or gain helps from each other whom they meet in shopping space. Ability of spatial identification fluctuates in the light of different gender roles, either in the physical world (Malinowski & Gillespie, 2001), or in the virtual space (Waller, 2000). Moreover, empirical research hosted by Tlauka et al., (2005) indicated that similar to gendered difference on spatial knowledge between men and women in physical real-world, it remains in computer-virtualized shopping space when using digital navigation tool. Nevertheless, there were other studies with distinct conclusions that men and women share comparable methods in certain respects of locating in shopping space (Avery, 1996), and female take less time on wayfinding in shopping mall and gender is not significant variable on time-consuming of wayfinding (Chebat et al., 2008). Freedom of shifting space has a long history of being privilege of men in literature on modernity, as well as reviews on gendered difference from evolutionary theoretical view (Jones et al., 2003), at the same time, it has also been affirmed by wayfinding studies with empirical methods (Harris, 1981; Miller & Santoni, 1986; Ward et al., 1986; Lawton & Charleston, 1996; Harrell et al., 2000). Men processed more expanded accessibility of applying mapping knowledge in their social communities while women were not, who showed “anxiety, uncertainty and hesitation” (Lawton & Charleston, 1996) when asked to operate wayfinding assignment.

Display & Decoration

Design elements in shopping space were categorized into two basic sorts: functional factors and aesthetic factors (Marans & Spreckelmeyer, 1982). Display and decoration in shopping space weigh in with design discourse, yet insufficient highlight had been laid

upon by empirical exploration through the view of marketing and environmental psychology, due to its intricate system of parameters (Ko & Rhee, 1994). Till now, there is severe inadequate relevant studies can be targeted. Influence of environment design consistent with the feedback of individual, in spite of that, had been interpreted by previously research (Zweigenhaft, 1976; Campbell, 1979; McElroy et al., 1990; Forsythe & Bailey, 1996). Furthermore, converging towards shopping space, utilities of design elements used in atmosphere for promoting positive reaction of consumers have been demonstrated by Wakefield and Baker (1998). Decoration in shopping space generally was presented as a tactic of exhibition comprising basic four aspects (Fiore et al., 2000): window display which is a directly perceived way acting as visual bridge connecting in-store world and outside passers-by; visualized merchandise display by which to project optimized pleasurable experience; three-dimension background containing roof, floor and wall, which furnishes a kind of theater space for performance of shopper’s gender identity; as well as miscellaneous kits such as advertisement stands, mannequins, props, sale signage, and LED. Although, associated studies were scarce, display design is still one of the most effective implements and silent strategies of persuasion that initiates purchase-decision of shoppers (Cahan & Robinson, 1984; Ko & Rhee, 1994). Recent empirical research (Kernsom & Sahachaisaeree, 2010) showed that differentiated applications of design elements in window display, such as size of text, clarity of slogan, tone of color, intensity of lighting, visibility access to in-store, frame of display, scale of window, created obvious variance on consumer’s cognitive and behavioral response. In contemporary hedonist culture, moreover, salience of display tactics of shopping space is pleasurable experience instead of utilitarian purpose (Fiore et al., 2000), which echoing stylish trends of stressing experientialism of shopping in materialistic panorama rather than doing mundane shopping for necessities.

Well-planned and deliberated displayed shopping space play an important role as resources of pleasure-hunting for consumers. Empirical research has advanced the connection between pleasure experience and environmental design by Fiore and

Kimle (1997). They explicated three kinds of pleasures respectively: firstly, sensory pleasure coming from stimulation of atmospherics; secondly, affective pleasure caused by emphasis on arousal of emotions; thirdly, cognitive pleasure resulted in production of meaningful visual messages. Unfortunately, the discussion on pleasurable experience had been already very adjacent to the issues of gender identity of shoppers, especially for the females, there is still scant endeavor presented by past and current studies.

ORGANISM-RESPONSE OF FEMALE SHOPPER

Who Go Shopping

Classification of shoppers was initiated by Stone (1954), four types were indicated as follow: the economic, the personalizing, the ethical and the apathetic. Bellenger et al. (1977) brought in the idea of “recreational shopper” as a newly type who is more proficient at exploring pleasure in shopping with more time consuming and accompanying, also without specific objective (Bellenger & Korgaonkar, 1980). Bloch et al (1994) also introduced another four-group consumer category: enthusiasts, traditionalists, grazers and minimalists.

By and large, consumers could be classified into two types, one as the task-oriented (problem-solving oriented) and the other as the recreational-oriented (hedonist-oriented). The former focuses on the result of shopping, which leads them to be practical; while the latter enjoys process of shopping, which causes a desired agent who is also high active performer of gender. Both of them, however, their gendered consciousness were modified by shopping practice and its environmental stimuli. Experience of recreational shopper in shopping space has received substantial attention from earlier researchers, including shopping was an enjoyable use of time (Bellenger & Korgaonkar, 1980); shopping primarily was to satisfy needs unrelated to the acquisition of needed products (Westbrook & Black, 1985); stores were visited to derive pleasure from the visit itself (Dawson et al., 1990; Reynolds & Beatty, 1999). In brief, pleasure-hunting consumer derives spontaneous hedonic response from the process of shopping activity.

Resistance as Subjectivity

Research (Bagozzi, 1992; Babin & Darden, 1995) showed “self-regulation” as a mediator of consumers’ behavior which shedding light on the reasons of why some consumers did not purchase anything in spite of hard promotional strategies manipulated. Atmospheric effects arouse diversified reactions on different consumers, such as task-oriented shoppers and recreational-oriented counterparts.

Although designers of retail stores have exhausted efforts to create purchase friendly ambience to keep shoppers staying for longer, empirical research point to there were complicated adherence between effects of design and reaction of consumer. The studies conducted by Kaltcheva and Barton (2006) displayed that recreational motivated consumers and the task-oriented counterparts gave different responses to the high design of arousal shopping space. The previous was easily vacillated by design tricks, while the latter was inactive or even resentful to the high exciting space. Similar to the predecessors’ empirical research, relationship between space design and shoppers was inconsistent (Donovan & Rossiter, 1982; Sherman et al., 1997).

Female Shopper as Pleasure Hunter

Motives of shopping and category of shoppers are linked to the issues of subjectivity and identity, which in this article, equivalent to the performance of gender. However, intention of shopping is more sophisticated comparing to types of shoppers. Tauber (1972) inventively imported shopping motives from the sociological perspective; Bloch et al., (1994), with the advent of mall culture, identified six driving forces of consumption for contemporary shopping fans: aesthetics seeking, escape from the mundane, exploration new world, flow experience, epistemic gains and social benefits; More pertinently findings were suggested by Falk (1997) who believed pleasure-acquisition was one of most important motivations by which consumer invested vast of time on ‘window shopping’.

Like Fischer (2003:63) presented, “A woman must be the queen of the store; she must feel that she is in a temple raised for her glory, her enjoyment, and her triumph.” For female shopper, in addition to necessary and mundane shopping as the role of

mother and wife, meaning of shopping is largely placed on symbolic and representational practice. In other words, women go shopping (not do shopping) mainly is in pursuit of pleasure, more concretely, for cognitive pleasure (Fiore et al., 2000). Cognitive pleasure is creation of meanings offered by space designer (Langrehr, 1991), who made a theatrical stage for female shopper to play ideal roles which underscores their gender identities.

DISCUSSION: DEEPEN GENDER AWARENESS

When it comes to topic of space design and issues of gender identity, a considerable contribution has been done by methodological and empirical researches of environmental design and consumer behavior, as well as theoretical debates on gender performance, however there is still a visible breach. Furthermore, case studies of space design have been swerved to environmental science, psychology, and engineering with their special interests onto the technological and operational dimensions in process of design, leaving aside its cultural, rhetorical and contextual natures which holding bigger portion on humane value.

Standpoint of this paper is not feminist criticism, but a neutral survey with the canon of gender.

Therefore, it is an action of occupying the gap between bias of concrete practical design research and leaning of abstract theoretical design studies. Gender identity is not a given or solid entity but a complex existence which is assembled by multi-dimension authorities such as mass media, urbanization, consumer culture and everyday life, since feminist criticism on department store of the nineteenth century in which women had been materialized and commoditized or subversive subject, aimed its fire to “(male) designers/planners/architects/retailers” had been proved neither unfair nor workable. Design is not everything, but a trivial spray in the recondite social sea. Not surprisingly, how does shopping space as cultural and social stage influence gender performance of major consumers - urban women, is largely under-research. This article displayed partial efforts on this issue.

Browsing high cited literatures on design of shopping space, the great mass of which, were marketing-oriented, neither cultural-centered nor gendered-

sensitive. Additionally, most of empirical researches went for the goal of description and explanation of results, which was less valuable compared to prediction and instruction to the following studies. This paper contributed to design community in two respects. First of all, with the predisposition of gender, it rearranged and synthesized a comprehensive findings of empirical research connecting space design and consumers. Although detailed elements of environment have been scrutinized from response of consumer, little attempt was made to examine for different gender identities which as the important mediator; meanwhile, much of which concentration came from marketing and business studies, not from eyes of design. Secondly, it combined theoretical contemplation with findings from field experiments, case studies and empirical researches in context of gender concern and design discourse. This synthetic method which is born with triggering potential to inspire innovated perspective of thinking about design issues.

Inasmuch as a huge bulk of empirical studies on the relevance between the environmental design and consumer's response has been proceeded where the emphasis was restricted onto the profitable and marketing fields, there is remaining ample gaps for design research to fill, which focusing on the ideal of whole-human and sustainability. Further research, hence, clinging to better understanding the value of gender issues in environmental design is still appealed to.

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